

FAITH HEALING AND MENTAL ILLNESS AMONG IBIBIO PEOPLE

Rosaline Ekpenyong Esen¹
Moses Idongesit Peters²

¹Psychiatric School of Nursing
Eket
rosalineesen@gmail.com
08032708247

²Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus
mosesidongesit@aksu.edu.ng, perfectakwastatr@gmail.com
09055479040

Abstract

This research work examined the roles of Faith Healing on Mental Illness among Ibibio People in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The researcher made use of explanatory model, holistic model and health belief model (HBM) as theoretical framework from which the synthesis of the three models, the researcher developed the Mental Health Seeking Behaviour Model (MHSBM). Ibibio speaking local government areas were purposively selected, and clustered into the 3 existing senatorial districts. Study participants were randomly selected from 16 Ibibio clans from randomly selected Ibibio speaking local government areas. 400 study respondents were engaged in interviews and their socio demographic data collected were presented using simple percentage method. Findings of the study were analyzed qualitatively in thematic analysis and content analysis with excerpts from the study participants. Findings of the study revealed that Ibibio people have great belief that mental illness is spiritually influenced and priority is given to treatment with spiritual powers which faith healers and traditional herbalists are the most patronized in terms of mental health services. It was concluded that, out of fear of being stigmatized; Ibibio people chose not to go to psychiatric hospitals for treatments to avoid the cultural implication of stigmatization which also contribute to the high dependency on faith healing and herbal treatments. The researcher among others recommended that the Ibibio people should be educated on mental health and illnesses in order to reduce the stigmatization and the belief in spiritual causes of mental illness among the people and throughout Akwa Ibom State.

Keywords: Mental illness, faith healing, spiritual belief, and Ibibio people

INTRODUCTION

Mental illness refers to a wide range of mental health disorders that affect the mood, thinking, behaviour and one's ability to function in social, work or family activities (APA, 2018). Mental health disorders constitute the major causes of disabilities worldwide, accounting for 37% of all healthy life years lost through disease (Jack-Ide, Uys and Middleton, 2013). It is also universal, affecting people of all countries and societies, regardless of age, gender and income. The prevalence of mental illness in the adult population at any given time is about 10% (Cuijpers and Stam 2003). Similarly, around 20% of all patients seen by primary health care providers have one or more mental health disorders.

Mental illness is a disabling, chronic condition that poses numerous challenges in its management and its risk factors for other health problems (Kabir, *et al.*, 2004). It bestows significant costs to the patient in terms of personal suffering, to the families as a result of the shift of burden of care

and life-time loss of productivity, and on the society at large (Esen and Peters, 2023). It is reported that mental and behavioural disorders are common, affecting more than 25% of all people at some time (Kabir, *et al.*, 2004). The prevalence of mental illness or disorder in some communities around the world makes availability of mental health care service a necessity. According to Azeem (2014), there is the need for community-based services to be delivered in the primary care setting to provide accessible and humane mental health care. In low-income and middle-income countries, support for primary care services to enable them to identify and treat people with mental disorders, with training, assistance, and supervision by available specialist mental health staff is the best way to extend mental health care to the population (Desjarlais, Eisenberg, Good, and Kleinman, 1995).

Societies across the world have different explanatory perspectives as it relates to the nature, causes and interventions for mental health problems (Ahmed, San and Nazar, 2015). These perspectives are as a result of certain aspects of the cultural practices of the society, which is entrenched in the way the people think, reason, act, and speak (Ahmed, *et al.*, 2015). The role of the community in the prevention and care of the mentally handicapped has now been widely acknowledged and is regarded as the most appropriate basis for the development of mental health programmes (Kabir *et al.*, 2004). Several studies have shown that knowledge of public attitude to mental illness and its treatment are vitally important prerequisite to the realization of successful community-based programmes (Esen and Peters, 2023). The norms, beliefs and customs within the individual's cultural environment, play a significant role in the recognition, care and management of mental disorder (Kabir *et al.*, 2004).

The health seeking behaviour of a community determines how health services are used and in turn the health outcomes of populations (Shaikh and Hatcher, 2005). Up to about 70% to 80% of the population of mentally ill belong to rural areas and first visit religious places and consult with the indigenous practitioner for their treatment (Subhudi, 2015). Factors that determine health seeking behaviour may be physical, socio-economic, cultural or political (Kroeger, 1983). Indeed, the utilisation of a health care system may depend on educational levels, economic factors, cultural beliefs and practices. Other factors include environmental conditions, socio-demographic factors, and knowledge about the facilities, gender issues, political environment, and the health care system itself (Ogunlesi, and Olanrewaju, 2010).

The Ibibio is the major tribe in Akwa Ibom State with a population of about 3.1 million which is about 60% of the state's population, going by the fact that the tribe forms about 16 of the 36 Local Government Areas of the state (Essien, 1990). The Ibibio is one of the oldest ethnic groups in Nigeria with its customs, culture, ethics and mores. These are determined by the belief system of the Ibibio people who are known for their distinct cultural belief on spirit beings and ancestors who live in the afterlife just like they in life (Essien, 1990). The belief also portrays the spirit being as having powers to influence human activities including health, economy, favour etc (Essien, 1990). Health challenges are usually associated with offences against the deities, gods and/or ancestors. This makes the appeasement of the gods or deities a necessity in health management in the history of Ibibio. The nature of the ailment is related to symptoms assumed or heard of (Essien, 1990). Divinity is usually resorted to in the cause of diagnosis. All these depend on the cultural background of the Ibibio. Almost everything in Ibibio is woven around religion. From childbirth, fertility, health, fortune and even influence in the society is assumed to be controlled in the spiritual realm (Oreva 2018). Among the Ibibio people, during some cultural activities by youths, it is believed that alcohol drink, cigarettes, marijuana, and hymn no. 4 are always carried along as they display to enable recharge of their mental psyche for the duties as especially masquerades (Peters, Bassey, Usoro & Samuel, 2022) which will later cause mental problems among the young people.

Different kinds of healers and healthcare services exist in Ibibio land. In today's Ibibio land, several orthodox and unorthodox health facilities abound. However, those specifically delineated for mental health are very few. Despite these, when mental health challenges arise, people seek help and

get what they assume as help. Sometimes and in some cases in Ibibio land, health challenge of one person in a family can disrupt the functioning of the entire family thus healthy living is both for the individual, the family and the society at large.

Mental illness is not alien to Ibibio culture and the Ibibio have attempted to demystify the problem so that permanent solution can be given to this illness which is assumed to affect the family members more than the mentally ill because Ibibio adage says “*Obut isi mummo Idat ase omum eyeneka Idat*” (The shame of madness does not bother the mad person, but members of his/her family). Various strategies have been adopted by different families to care, treat and manage the mentally ill with the desire of returning them to normalcy.

With the low level of orthodox mental healthcare delivery in Nigeria, the mentally ill seek other alternatives to solving their problems. Gureje and Lasebikan (2006) observed that the service gap left by orthodox mental health practice in Nigeria is filled by traditional, spiritual, faith healing and complementary medicine, the use of which is widespread in most communities, as lay perception of mental disorders are still rooted in super-natural belief systems especially among the Ibibio people, and therefore considered untreatable with western medicine. This background provides the gap as in investigating the roles of faith healing as a preferred mental health care alternative among the Ibibio people which this research work sought to fill.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to investigate the curative roles of faith healers in mental illness among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study was designed specifically:

1. To investigate if spiritual explanations make faith healers a preferred healing method for the mental illness in Ibibio.
2. To investigate if belief system is responsible for the choice of faith healers as preferred treatment of mental illness in Ibibio
3. To investigate if yielded results make faith healers a choice of health seeking behaviour for treatment of mental illness in Ibibio.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Mental illness

Mental health according to Stein (2013), could be seen as the successful performance of mental functions resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships, and the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity. The reverse is mental illness. Mohr (2003) quoted American Psychiatric Association (APA) that mental illness is considered a clinically significant behavioural or psychological syndrome experienced by a person and marked by distress, disability or the risk of suffering disability or loss of freedom. It could be marked by alterations in thinking, mood or behaviour that cause distress, impaired ability to function or both.

According to Stein, Phillips, Bolton, Fulford, Sadler, and Kendler, (2010), a mental disorder is a psychological [syndrome](#) or pattern which is associated with [distress](#) (e.g. via a painful [symptom](#)), [disability](#) (impairment in one or more important areas of functioning), increased risk of death, or causes a significant loss of autonomy; however it excludes normal responses such as [grief](#) from loss of a loved one, and also excludes [deviant behaviour](#) for political, religious, or societal reasons not arising from a dysfunction in the individual. Mental Health Association in Forsyth County (2009) defines mental illness as a disease of the brain that causes mild to severe disturbances in thought and/or behaviour, resulting in an inability to cope with life's ordinary demands and routines. There are more than 200 classified forms of mental illness (Mental Health Association, 2009). Some of the more common disorders are: clinical depression, bipolar disorder, dementia, schizophrenia and anxiety disorders. Mental illness therefore involves expression of distress, an inability to be independent as well as alteration of mood, behaviour or thought due to a malfunctioning of a certain human organ

responsible for these or any of these (Mental Health Association, 2009). However, some mental illness may be expressed in only one of the above listed characteristics. There are people who suddenly talk more than usual or express more self-pity or self-pride than used to be. Such can be identified as having mental disorders.

While there are over 200 classified forms of mental illness, Mental Health Association in Forsyth County (2011) identified five (5) major categories of mental illness as:

- [Anxiety Disorders](#)
- [Mood Disorders](#)
- [Schizophrenia/Psychotic Disorders](#)
- [Dementias](#)
- [Eating Disorders](#)

Causes of mental illness are varied. According to Krupansky (2017), there are three broad categories of factors influencing mental illness:

1. Biological factors.
2. Life experience and environmental factors.
3. Psychological and individual factors, including resilience.

Etiology is the technical term for determining the cause of a disorder (Mental Health Association, (2011). Psychiatrists explore the history of the patient to diagnose the possible cause of their case and relate this history with symptoms manifested to proffer possible remedies.

Mental illness is very prevalent in South Africa, yet the country lacks many of the necessary resources and policies needed to execute an effective mental health strategy. Many factors including [violence](#), [communicable disease](#), and urbanisation have increased the prevalence of [mental disorders](#) in the country (MHSA and WHO, 2007). The way in which these mental disorders are treated has changed over the years. For a while, [mental health care](#) was mainly [institutionalised](#) (MHSA and WHO, 2007). However, in 1997, following the White Paper Act, the South African government moved to [deinstitutionalize](#) mental health care and relegate it to the [primary care](#) setting. However, current data indicates that the goal of deinstitutionalization and effective primary mental care has still not been fulfilled (MHSA and WHO, 2007).

Health Seeking Behaviour and Mental Illness

Research on health seeking behaviour during mental illness has been done in several areas of the world though not much has been done in the South Southern region of Nigeria. Evidences abound of how the mentally ill and their relatives approach the challenge of mental illness in their bid to seek cure or relief. According Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009), it is widely acknowledged that sub-Saharan Africa is deficient in providing prompt and effective professional mental health services, which are needed to avoid chronic illness and the establishment of irreversible squealed.

Equally, Burns and Tomita (2015) observed that there is good evidence for a considerable mental health treatment gap in low-income and middle-income countries (LMICs) due to a lack of adequate infrastructure, human resources and treatment options. This is nowhere more apparent than on the African continent, where data from the World Health Organization's Atlas Project on mental health shows widespread, systematic and long-term neglect of resources for mental health care in low income and middle-income countries (Burns and Tomita, 2015).

Additionally, Jimenez, Bartels, Cardenas, Daliwal, and Alegría (2012) posit that beliefs concerning the causes of mental illness may help explain why there are significant disparities in the rates of formal mental health service use. Most cultures especially in Africa have been found to adopt the complementary and traditional medical practices to solve the problems of mental ill health. According to Sorsdahl, Stein, Grimsrud, Seedat, Flisher, Williams, and Myer, (2009), several studies have shown that alternative practitioners play an important role in addressing mental health care needs in South Africa by offering culturally appropriate treatment. In many traditional African belief systems,

mental health problems are perceived as due to ancestors or by bewitchment and traditional healers and religious advisors are viewed as having expertise in these areas (Nattrass, 2005; Freeman, Lee and Vivian, 1994; Mbanga, Niehaus and Mzamo, 2002).

Epidemiological studies across different nations show that only about one third of people with a mental disorder consult the mental health services, others seeking help from different sectors, such as the family physicians, general practitioners, or other physicians, depending on the type of health system of the country. Even in the high-income countries, such as USA, Canada, Italy, and Netherlands, a substantial number of patients with mental health problems don't seek treatment from the mental health sector, and rather seek help in the general medical sector, which includes general physicians or general practitioners, and are referred to the psychiatrists later, if required (Andrews, Issakidis, and Carter, 2001).

In India, the mental health resources are very low compared with high-income countries. According to a recent estimate, the country has just 0.25 psychiatric beds per 10,000 population, 0.2 psychiatrists, 0.03 clinical psychologists, 0.05 psychiatric nurses, and 0.03 social workers per 100,000 of the population (Alegria, Bijl, Lin, Walters, and Kessler, 2000). The facilities for psychiatric treatment are generally available in general hospital psychiatric units, mental hospitals, and office-based practice. Besides these, the patients, depending on the availability and accessibility, may consult a non-psychiatric physician, general practitioner, lay counselor, local religious leaders, or traditional faith healer (Andrews, Issakidis, and Carter, 2001).

On the perceived efficacy of the alternative and traditional mental health care which may have sustained their belief and patronage in low – income countries, researchers have discovered relative levels of efficacy. Abbo (2011), reviewed profiles and outcome of traditional healing practices for severe mental illnesses in two districts of Eastern Uganda and observed that for a cohort of patients with severe mental illness attending traditional healers there was a general trend for symptom scales to show a reduction at the 3- and 6-month follow-ups. However, in terms of patients' cutoff points for diagnosis, the general improvement at 3 months was greatest in patients with mania (54.0percent), less so with psychotic depression (42.0percent), and least with schizophrenia (14.8percent). At 6 months, the percentage of patients who showed an improvement was as follows: mania (58.3percent), psychotic depression (46.4percent), and schizophrenia (30.7percent) (Abbo, 2011).

However, Burns and Tomita (2015), in a study traditional and religious healers in the pathway to care for people with mental disorders in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis, noted that in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), a considerable proportion of individuals seeking care for mental disorders consult traditional and religious healers in their pathway to mental health care. Such early involvement of healers may result in delays in the care pathway; a potential barrier to early identification and intervention. This however portrays a lack of effective cure of the mental illness by the traditional and religious healers which may result in the patient and relatives seeking other means, usually orthodox, of treatment for the ailment (Burns and Tomita, 2015).

Burns and Tomita maintained that traditional and religious healers have been identified as herbalists, diviners and faith healers in this study, the level of patronage of each in Nigeria and other African countries will paint a clearer picture of health seeking behaviour for the mentally ill in these areas thus providing the review upon which this study is premised. Sorsdahl *et al.*, (2009) in their study traditional healers in the treatment of common mental disorders in South Africa, observed that of the participants who sought treatment (regardless of whether they met lifetime DSM-IV criteria for a disorder or not), 21percent were treated by Western practitioners, 13percent were treated by alternative practitioners, and 7percent by a combination of both Western, and alternative practitioners. Of the subjects who sought treatment from alternative medicine, 6percent sought treatment from a traditional healer, 7percent of the sample sought treatment from a spiritual or religious advisor, and 2percent by another type of healer. However, while 14percent of study participants sought treatment

from a Western practitioner exclusively, only 2percent sought treatment from a traditional healer exclusively (Sorsdahl *et al.*, 2009).

Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) in a study; preferred treatment for mental illness among Southwestern Nigerians showed that 844 (41percent) study participants indicated spiritual healers as their preferred treatment option, whereas 634 (30percent) indicated traditional healers and 600 (29percent) indicated Western medicine. They also found that the factors that were independently associated with preference for spiritual or traditional healers included being female, having a lower level of education, having never cared for a person with mental illness, and endorsement of supernatural causal beliefs. Further analysis of the data by Adewuya and Makanjuola (2009) showed that the bulk of the gender difference was in the spiritual healers' option alone, with no gender difference in the option of traditional healers.

In India, a middle income countries outside Africa, [Mishra](#), [Nagpal](#), [Chadda](#) and [Sood](#) (2011), observe that nearly one third of the patients consulted a traditional faith healer or an alternative medicine practitioner at some point of course of their illness. Similarly, more than 80percent of the patients also consulted a non-psychiatric physician at some time for their mental health problem. However, a recent study from a psychiatric hospital in the state of Madhya Pradesh (Central India) found faith healers as the first contact of help in 68% of the total sample. Most of the patients in these studies suffered from psychotic disorders of different types.

In the first two studies, having been conducted in the cities of Delhi and Bangalore, majority of the patients were from urban background, whereas in the third study, nearly 70percent of the sample was from a rural background. Another reason for a high percentage of patients going to faith healers as the first contact in the study could be that number of psychiatrists in the state of Madhya Pradesh is much lower compared with the places of other studies.

Effiong and Albert (2016) in their study; Pathways to Psychiatric Care among Patients with Schizophrenia in Nigeria, it was found that majority of participants (76.8percent) patronized non-orthodox treatment facility as their first treatment option in help seeking for mental disorders. This, the study showed, comprises (65.7percent) of those who patronized religious healers as their first contact and (11.1percent) of participants who visited traditional healers for their first treatment attention. The study also showed that 41.7percent visited a second religious treatment centre and 36.8percent visited a third before attention in a tertiary psychiatric facility.

Faith Healing and Mental Illness

In their study; Healers and healing practices of mental illness in India: The role of proposed eclectic healing model, [Biswal](#), [Subudhi](#), and [Acharya](#), (2017), posit that healing process in religious places is based on religious prayers, ritual activities, and the process is almost same for the all the victims. It is believed among people that the religious prayers and pooja (*hawan*) would help to reduce the effect of the mental illness (Campion and Bhugra, 1997; [Biswal](#), *et al.*, 2017). The ritual prayer is accompanied with some practices such as fasting or eating raw fruits and performing prayer for a regular period (Padmavati, Thara, and Corin, 2015). According to [Biswal](#), *et al.*, (2017), these healing practices are performed by the priest of the temple or father of the church or the imam of the mosque. The healers usually follow the same pattern of offering prayers for all patients. This type of religious healing is widely used for managing mental illness and is the first choice among people to cure the mental illness (Padmavati, *et al.*, 2015; Raguram, Venkateswaran, Ramakrishna, Weiss, 2002). According to [Biswal](#) *et al.*, (2017), majority (46%) believe that offering prayer is the only way to cure mental illness.

In a study by Thara, Islam, and Padmavati, (1998), they reported that interestingly, six patients found an improvement in their condition through religious healing. The factors that contribute to preference for religious healing include such considerations as nearness to home (20%), safety level of

the religious places (Rathinavel, Prashanth, Kasthuri, Kumar, and Chandrashekar, 2010), failure of modern treatment (80%), and influence of family members and friends (66%) (Biswal *et al.*, 2017). Unlike, other forms of the physical disease which takes relatively less time, mental illnesses take more time to cure. A lack of understanding and knowledge about mental illness among the public helps them form the opinion that modern treatment is a failure system for mental illness (Biswal *et al.*, 2017).

Krans (2013) in his study; Faith Healing: Belief in God Improves Psychiatric Treatment Outcomes, those with a mental illness and faith in a higher power fare better in treatment than non-believers. The results of the study indicated that over the course of treatment, belief in God, but not religious affiliation, was associated with greater likelihood of treatment response, as well as greater reductions in depression and self-harm and greater increases in psychological well-being," the study states. Krans in his study concluded that findings may suggest that faith is a general cognitive attribute representing an optimistic mental schema that can generalize to spiritual, medical, and perhaps other domains as well.

Healing of mental illness through religious practices was a key element of early Christianity (American Psychiatric Association APA, 2019). In the early twentieth century such healing was associated with blue-collar and rural Fundamentalists, but religious healing practices have gained widespread acceptance by many middle-class, conservative Christian groups. "Evil demons" are now equated with envy, pride, avarice, hatred, and obsessions with alcohol and gambling. Many psychotherapeutic techniques of modern Christian healers appear to be rediscoveries of psychoanalytic insights expressed in religious metaphors (APA, 2019). Most responsible healers encourage clients to seek medical and psychiatric help, especially for serious mental disorders. Psychiatrists need not share patients' religious beliefs, but for treatment to be effective these beliefs must be understood and respected (APA, 2019).

Over time, society and medicine have progressed, pushing tradition, ritual, superstition, and religion aside in favour of more evidence-based practices (Hippocratic, 2019). Blood transfusions replaced leeches and daily medicine replaced prayers. Yet still today, faith-based practices are the main source of healing for many communities internationally. Faith healers, who are traditionally trusted and respected members of many societies around the world, have the ability to provide certain services that can be invaluable for individuals suffering from a variety of ailments (Hippocratic, 2019). However, it must also be acknowledged that a lack of proper medical attention and a reliance strictly on religion or ritual to treat illness can lead to further pain or even death (Hippocratic, 2019).

According to Swartz and Kpobi (2018), the use of non-biomedical methods to treat mental disorders in developing countries, like Ghana, has long been acknowledged. [The World Health Organisation \(WHO\)](#) estimates that about 80% of people who need mental health care in developing countries go to indigenous or faith healers for care (Swartz and Kpobi, 2018). In many African countries traditional and faith healers are viewed as community leaders and their views are likely to reflect those of their patients. Consequently, biomedical professionals who treat patients who are also seeking help from indigenous and faith healers would benefit from understanding the different beliefs about different disorders. This can then form an important part of clinical training and practice (Swartz and Kpobi, 2018).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Health Belief Model

The Health Belief Model

The major components of this model include:

Perceived susceptibility: Perceived susceptibility refers to beliefs about the likelihood of getting a disease or condition.

Perceived severity: Feelings about the seriousness of contracting an illness or of leaving it untreated include evaluations of both medical and clinical consequences (for example, death, disability, and pain) and possible social consequences (such as effects of the conditions on work, family life, and social relations). The combination of susceptibility and severity has been labelled as perceived threat.

Perceived benefits: Even if a person perceives personal susceptibility to a serious health condition (perceived threat), whether this perception leads to behaviour change will be influenced by the person's beliefs regarding perceived benefits of the various available actions for reducing the disease threat. Thus, individuals exhibiting optimal beliefs in susceptibility and severity are not expected to accept any recommended health action unless they also perceive the action as potentially beneficial by reducing the threat.

Perceived barriers: The potential negative aspects of a particular health action, perceived barriers, may act as impediments to undertaking recommended behaviours. A kind of none-conscious, cost-benefit analysis occurs wherein individuals weigh the actions expected benefits with perceived barriers, "It could help me, but it may be expensive, have negative side effects, be unpleasant, inconvenient, or time-consuming." Thus, "combined levels of susceptibility and severity provide the energy or force to act and the perception of benefits (minus barriers) provide a preferred path of action"

Cues to action: Various early formulations of the HBM included the concept of cues that can trigger actions. For example, thought that readiness to take action (perceived susceptibility and perceived benefits) could only be potentiated by other factors, particularly by cues to instigate action, such as bodily events, or by environmental events, such as media publicity.

Self-efficacy: Self-efficacy is defined as "the conviction that one can successfully execute the behaviour required to produce the outcomes". Self-efficacy expectations from outcome expectations, defined as a person's estimate that a given behaviour will lead to certain outcomes.

Amendments to the Health Belief model, as stated by Glanz, Rimer and Viswanath (2008), were made as late as 1988 to incorporate emerging evidence within the field of psychology about the

role of self-efficacy in decision-making and behavior which is a major dimension in the choice of faith healer as a preferred mental health care service among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State.

METHODOLOGY

An ethnographic research design was adopted with a multi-stage type of data collection approach. Ethnographic research allows the researcher to immerse his or herself in the cultural practices of the people in order to close social distance and gain proper understanding of the social problem from the cultural context of the people. This type of research design facilitates a search for information to gain insight on substantial issues in the study because of its exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory potentials.

The study area was Akwa Ibom state. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria, created on the 23rd of September 1987, with Uyo as its capital. Akwa Ibom is one of Nigeria's 36 states, with a population of over five million people (NPC, 2006). The study was conducted among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. The Ibibio people are a coastal people in southern Nigeria (Cole and Derk, 2012). They are mostly found in Akwa Ibom, Cross River, and on the Eastern Part of Abia. They are related to the Anaang, Igbo and Efik peoples. During the colonial period in Nigeria, the Ibibio Union asked for recognition by the British as a sovereign nation (Offiong, 1983). The Annang, Efik, and Oron share personal names, culture, and traditions with the Ibibio, and speak closely related varieties of Ibibio-Efik which are more or less mutually intelligible (Okon, 1984). Masks are a primary aspect of art made by the Ibibio.

The researchers adopted a big-net approach (Fatterman, 2010) to gather information from the study participants. Participant observation, in-depth interview (II), key informant interview (KII), and focus group discussions (FGDs) were used by the researchers to obtain primary data. Secondary data were collected through published materials and internet sources.

FINDINGS

Socio-demographic Data of Participants

The socio-demographic distribution of the sampled study implies that the total number of the study participants was 400, the males constituted of 303 (75.8%) and the females constituted 97 (24.2%). The analysis of this shows that the views being expressed in this study were representative of both male and female, with the male study participants being the majority. Under the age characteristics, the majority of study participants (122/30.5%) were between ages 41 - 50 years. In the same analysis, 102 (25.5%) of study participants were between the ages of 51 - 60 years, 72 (18.0%) of participants were 60 years and above, 56 (14%) were between the ages of 31 - 40 years, and 48 (12%) were 21 - 30 years. This implies that majority of the study participants were of the older age of the study population's sample which satisfied the most targeted sample of the study.

Also observed was that under marital characteristics, that the highest in this category were the married with 203 (50.8%) of the study participants, this was followed by the widow/widowers with 78 (19.5%). The next in this category was singles with 45 (11.2%), 34 (8.5%) were divorced, 27 (6.8%) were co-habiting, while the least in this category were the separated with 13 (3.2%). Therefore, a large proportion of the study participants were the married, while the least part of the study population's sample were the co-habiting. Under the educational status of the study participants, those with secondary education (SSCE) were the highest in number with 213 (53.2%), those with primary education (FLSC) were the second in this category with 91 (22.8%), this is followed with those with no formal education were 49 (12.2%), while the least in this category were those with tertiary education (NCE, OND, HND, Bsc, and Msc) were 47 (11.8%). This implies that most participants in this study were of average educational status, and are educated enough to respond to the questions and give valid opinion on the subject matter under investigation as undertaken by the researcher.

Under religious affiliation, the result of the study participants shows that the highest group in

this category 337 (84.2%) were Christians, 60 (15%) were traditional worshipers, none of the study participants was found to practice Islam, while 3 (0.8%) were into other form of religious practices. This further implies that the researchers had study participants that cut across large segments and varieties of socio-demographic characteristics which are important in obtaining a balanced and unbiased view from study participants.

Spiritual Explanations and Faith Healing

Spirituality is a key characteristic of Ibibio people right from before the advent of Christianity through the era of Christianity which is still ongoing. Information gathered through discussions and interviews revealed that faith healing is rooted in both traditional religion and Christianity. The majority of the study participants agreed that in many cases of faith healing in mental illness treatment, the faith healers combine prayers and herbs to achieve both spiritual and psychological balance.

Emerging from discussions and interviews is the fact that mental illness has been considered to be a spiritual problem instead of physical problem among Ibibio people. The spiritual explanations given to mental illness by the study participants depict the high level of patronage given to faith healing treatment of mental illness among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. One of the participants aged 39 years, in his responses said;

Over the years we have witnessed people who had mental problems and were healed from different churches. When I said that madness is a spiritual problem some people will argue without one taking stock of the illness in this part of the world. For the simple fact that these churches are healing the mad people, whether they used prayer and other things, the fact remains that most of the mental illness is a spiritual problem and it takes spiritualists to handle spiritual cases. This has been confirmed even in this community (Emenim 39, interview conducted on 24/9/2019).

Study participants were of the opinion that mental illness is the type of illness that is mainly control by spiritual forces like demons which in some cases do manifest through the victims with great strength and power. One of the study participants aged 61 years in his responses, reported that;

See, madness is a spiritual thing don't allow anybody to deceive you because I have seen demons manifest through mad people. Also how will you explain the fact that these mad people have been eating from waste bins and drink dirty water from gutters and they are not sick? It is not a normal physical sickness. There are spiritual forces responsible for this type of sickness and these forces are demons. These demons keep them save from infections and given them power to with stand people who sometimes want to catch them and tie them. That is why in so many cases if you don't have strong spiritual power, you cannot hold them. Catch them or command them (Okpo 61, interviewed on 24/9/2019)

Beliefsystem and Faith Healing

According to narratives from discussions, faith healing has been a long standing practice among the Ibibio people in the area of mental illness treatment. The practice has yield results as many have recovered and returned to their normal lives, some have gotten married from the same community which they went for treatment. One of the key informants in his narratives said;

I have been into healing madness and mentally ill person for many years now. I have treated many mad people and have delivered results for many years now. As a pastor, it was when a mad man was brought to me for the first time to pray for. I did love this man and placed him on fasting. When I came out one day to

see that he defecated and eat his feces, my heart was broken completely. I asked myself of what this man would have done to do this to himself. Did he kill somebody? When I went to bed that night 3 men came to me in a vision of the night and took me to out to show me herbs I can give to mad people in order to cure them. I woke and gave it to the man and he later got healed and went back. Since then I have used those herbs to cure many up till today (Jomo 58, interview conducted on 23/8/2019).

Ibibio people have over the years, patronized faith healing for mental illness, and have built a good level of trust in this method of treatment for mental illness over others. This according to the majority of the study participants is based on the existence of high level of believes that mental illness is more of spiritual problem than physical problem. Most of the participants showed high level of trust in faith healing treatment. Discussion revealed that whenever such health challenge occurs among the Ibibio people, the first treatment approach that will be recommended for the patient's family is faith healing treatment.

One of the study participants aged 68 years reported that;

I remember when my sister developed mental problem. The first thing I taught of God because I know that He can do everything so I took her to my pastor who prayed for her. Though my pastor offered only prayers for her and she was there for some days without proper recovery though she was calm a bit, I was later refer to another church were the pastor used herbs and prayers and for few days she was okay. The pastor told me to allow her to stay for few weeks for proper monitoring and examination to be sure before we leave with her, and we did. Today she is okay (Akaninyene 68, interviewed on 22/8/2019)

Curative roles and Faith Healing

Information gathered from discussions and interviews revealed that there are cases where mentally ill patients are returned from psychiatric hospital to spiritual homes. Key informants who were practitioners of faith healing confirmed that there are cases where mentally ill patients are brought to them from psychiatric hospitals after they might have received orthodox treatments from psychiatric hospitals and other orthodox treatment providers. One of the key informants from Efa village in Etinan Local Government Area in his narratives said;

I have been into this practice since the LORD called me into this ministry. For many years now I have received, treated, and send back many mentally ill persons who were brought to me for treatment. Some of them were brought from psychiatric hospitals to me for treatment, and I still have some of them with me as you can see. Some of them have recovered and I have negotiated with people that have works like farm works, construction works and other works which they can do to help them by giving them such works to do for some payment so that they can survive since their family members who brought them have abandon them. I don't know whether they lost faith in them that God can no longer heal and restore them. But God has been showing his faithfulness by restoring them (Akan 50, interview conducted on 23/8/2019).

Information gotten through interviews from key informants who were faith healers across the Ibibio land revealed that mentally ill patients were brought from where they were receiving orthodox treatments to their places. One of them in his responses said;

I inherited this ministry from my father. He asked me to give him goat before he could hand over to me, and I did. Since I took over, many cases of mental ill patients have been brought to me, and I have ministered to them and the good LORD has been faithful in healing them and to Him be the Glory. This has made people to bring their relative with mental problem from afar. There are cases where patients are brought from hospitals to me and prayer, and ministered to them (Power 47, interview conducted on 25/8/2019).

Emergence from discussions and interviews is the high level of patronage of faith healing among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State due to said results reported by the people and as testified of by the faith healing practitioners. Faith healing treatment has taken a deep root into Ibibio people especially in the area of mental illness.

DISCUSSING OF FINDINGS

Emerging findings from discussions and interviews show that mental illness is a known health condition with high degree of stigmatization among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State. WHO (1994) gives credence to this finding, stating that; there is an increasing awareness of mental illness as a significant cause of morbidity throughout the whole world. This placed a great burden on the family of the mentally ill person. It is family responsibility to take care of the patient and take charge of all the cost and expenditure incurred through the process of seeking treatment for the patient. On general knowledge about mental illness, findings show that Ibibio people consider mental illness to be caused by spiritual forces. There is a high level of belief that some spiritual forces are responsible for mental illness. This situation and belief system greatly affects the mental health seeking behaviour of the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State.

On choice of treatment for mental illness, finding`s show that since Ibibio people believe that mental illness is spiritually controlled, the first and best choice of treatment as revealed through discussions and interviews is faith healing or traditional herbalist, who will be able to deal with the spirits in order to deliver the person involved. Credence to this finding is gotten from Kabir et al (2004) who posit that community attitude and beliefs, play a role in determining help-seeking behaviour and successful treatment of the mentally ill. The results which were said to have been recorded in mental illness treatment by the faith healing and traditional herbal practitioners, and the fact that people withdraw their patients from psychiatric hospital to faith healers and herbalists seem to have certified their belief that mental illness is a spiritual problem with a physical manifestation. Most of the faith healers and traditional herbalists have been a stopping point in mental illness treatment for many who have mentally ill patients across Ibibio land and its environs. Findings further showed that there are faith healers who combine prayers with herbs and roots for mental illness treatment, while there are traditional herbalists who combine herbs and root with spiritual activities of African Traditional religion.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of faith healing on mental illness among Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Mental illness to the Ibibio people is spiritually controlled ailment which needs spiritual intervention for successful and effective treatment. The most preferred treatment for mental illness among the Ibibio people is the spiritualist`s treatment which include faith healing and traditional herbalist treatments. There is high degree of stigmatization among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State in relation to mental illness. Therefore, out of fear of being stigmatized will choose not to take their mentally ill patients to psychiatric hospital in order not to reveal the fact that they have madness or lunatic spirit in the family. The researchers recommended that Government and non-government organizations should embark on proper education of the people on the causes of mental illness in order to replace or reduce the degree

of belief that mental illness is a spiritual problem.

REFERENCES

- Abbo, C. (2011). Profiles and outcome of traditional healing practices for severe mental illnesses in two districts of Eastern Uganda. *Global Health Action*. 4(7117); 1 – 15p
- Adewuya, A. & Makanjuola, R. (2009) Preferred Treatment for Mental Illness Among Southwestern Nigerians. *Psychiatric Services* 60(1); 121-124
- American Psychiatric Association (2019). Modern Christian Healing of Mental Illness. Retrieved online on 24th July, 2019.
- Azeem, K. (2014). Perceived barriers and facilitators to mental health help-seeking in young people: a systematic review. *BMC Psychiatry* 10:113
- Biswal, R., Subudhi, C., & Acharya, S. C. (2017). Healers and healing practices of mental illness in India: The role of proposed eclectic healing model. *Journal of Health Research and Review in Developing Countries*. Vol. 4(3). 89-95.
- Cuijpers P, Stam H. (2003). Burnout among relatives of psychiatric patients attending psycho-educational support groups. *Psychiatry Services*. 51(3): 375-379p.
- Campion J, & Bhugra D. (1997). Experiences of religious healing in psychiatric patients in South India. *Society of Psychiatry. Psychiatry Epidemiology* 32:215-221.
- Cole, H. M., and Dierk, D. (2012) *Invention and Tradition: the Art of Southeastern Nigeria*. Prestel.
- Desjarlais R, Eisenberg L, Good B, & Kleinman, A (1995) *World mental health: Problems and priorities in low income countries*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Effiong, J. H. & Albert, U. K. (2016). Pathways to Psychiatric Care among Patients with Schizophrenia in Uyo, Nigeria. *International Neuropsychiatric Disease Journal* 5(4): 1-10.
- Esen, R. E. & Peters, M. I. (2023). Mental Illness and The Panacea of Orthodox Medicine Patronage Among Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities (GJCH)*. Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 2(1): 2 -16
- Esen, R. E. & Peters, M. I. (2023). Herbalists and Mental Health Seeking Behaviour among the Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria. *Social Sciences and Management International Journal* Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 4(1): 1 -14.
- Essien, O. E. (1990). *Grammar of the Ibibio Language*. University Press Limited.
- Fetterman, D. M. (2010). *Ethnography: Step-by-Step*. SAGE Publication, Inc. California. 42-50p.
- Gureje O, and Lasebikan V. O. (2006). Use of Mental Health Services in a Developing Country: Results from the Nigerian Survey of Mental Health and Well-being. *Society of Psychiatry. Psychiatry Epidemiology*. 41(1):44-49.
- Hippocratic (2019). Faith Healers and Better Mental Health. Retrieved online on 24th July, 2019. 12-20p.
- Jimenez, D. E., Bartels, S. J., Cardenas, V., Daliwal, S. S. and Alegria, M. (2012) Cultural Beliefs and Mental Health Treatment Preferences of Ethnically Diverse Older Adult Consumers in Primary Care. *American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. 20(6): 533–542.
- Kabir, M., Iliyasu, Z., Abubakar, I. S. and Aliyu, M. H. (2004) Perception and beliefs about mental illness among adults in Karfi village, northern Nigeria *BMC International Health and Human Rights* (2)44:3-12.
- Kroeger A. (1983), Anthropological and Socio-medical Health Care Research in Developing Countries. *Social Sciences Journal of Medicines* 1983; 17:147-161.
- Jack-Ide, I. O., Uys, L., Middleton, L. E. (2013). Caregiving experiences of families of persons with serious mental health problems in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing*. 22(2):170-179.
- Mental Health Association (2009). *Mental Health Report 2008*. www.mha.org
- Mental Health Association (2011). *Mental Health Report 2010 Forsyth County*. www.mha.org

- Mishra, N., Nagpal, S. S., Chadda, R. K. and Sood, M. (2011). Help-seeking behaviour of patients with mental health problems visiting a tertiary care center in North India. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*. 53(3): 234–238.
- Offiong, D. A. (1983). "Social Relations and Witch Beliefs among the Ibibio of Nigeria". *Journal of Anthropological Research*. 39 (1): 81–95p
- Okon, G. P. (1984). The Phenomenon of Witch[c]raft Among the Ibibio People of Nigeria. Pontificia Universitas Urbaniana, Facultas Philosophica.
- Stein, D., Philips, H. Bolton, G. Fuldord, S., Sadler, R. & Kendler, Y. (2010). The prevalence and distribution of major depression in a national community sample: The National Comorbidity Survey. *American Journal of Psychiatry* 1994(151):979–86.
- Oreva, d. (2018). Ibibio Culture: A brief walk into the lives of one of Africa's oldest people. Retrieved online from <https://www.pulse.ng/lifestyle>. On 13th January, 2019. 12 – 14p.
- Padmavati R., Thara R. & Corin E. (2015). A qualitative study of religious practices by chronic mentally ill and their caregivers in South India. *International Journal of Societal Psychiatry*. 51:139-149
- Peters, M. I., Bassey, A. E., Usoro, N. A. & Samuel, M. E. (2022). Hymn No 4: A Novel Psychoactive Substance Consumption among Ibibio Youths of The Niger Delta Region. *International Journal of Education and Science Development (IJESD)* Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 1(2): 19–44
- Rathinavel, I, Prashanth, N. R., Kasthuri, P., Kumar, C. N. & Chandrashekar, H. (2010). Why do mentally ill patients seek religious places for treatment? *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*. 52: 280-281.
- Stein, G. (2013). Perceived need for mental health care and barriers to care in the Maryland. USA. *Social Psychiatry Epidemiology* 36:906–925
- WHO, (2008). Traditional Medicine. *Fact Sheet* 134. 123-127p.
- Shaikh, B. T. & Hatcher, J. (2005), Health Seeking Behaviour and Health Service Utilization in Pakistan: Challenging the Policy Makers. *Journal of Public Health (Oxford)* 2005; 1:49-54.
- Sorsdahl, K., Stein, D. J., Grimsrud, A., Seedat, S., Flisher, A. J. Williams, D. R. and Myer, L. (2009). Traditional Healers in the Treatment of Common Mental Disorders in South Africa. *Journal Nervous Mental Disorder* 197: 434–441.
- Subhudi, M. (2015) Barriers to help-seeking by men: a review of socio-cultural and clinical literature with particular reference to depression. *Journal of Affected Disorder* 71:1–9